

The Data Revolution is Now:

How Communication Contributes to Cyberinfrastructure Organizing

By Cassandra Hayes

What was this project about?

Cyberinfrastructure (CI) = the network of supercomputers and professional community in the US dedicated to enabling the use of big data for research (Stewart et al., 2010)

CI Organizing

Self-organizing systems theory “seeks to explain the emergence of patterned behavior in systems that are initially in a state of disorganization” (Contractor, 1994, p. 51).

For this research...

I analyzed 31 foundational documents on CI, NSF budget requests from 2002-2022 mentions of CI, and 40 interviews with CI professionals carried out 2016-2022.

Through this project, I found that the organizing of the **CI community** works through **rhetoric, rituals, and riots.**

So what?

Communication plays a key role in the organizing that supports critical infrastructure systems such as CI.

REFERENCES

- Contractor, N. S. (1994). Self-organizing systems perspective in the study of organizational communication. In B. Kovacic (Ed.), *New approaches to organizational communication* (pp. 39-66). State University of New York Press.
- Stewart, C. A., Simms, S., Plale, B., Link, M., Hancock, D. Y., & Fox, G. C. (2010, October). What is cyberinfrastructure. In *Proceedings of the 38th annual ACM SIGUCCS fall conference: navigation and discovery* (pp. 37-44). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1878335.1878347>

Rhetoric

I argue that a distinct American infrastructure myth works to justify arguments for digital technologies.

Symbolic Narratives

The myth that builds off past stories of frontiers and industrialization to offer romanticized origins for CI.

Constituting Community

Myths help conceptualize an identity of technocratic experts whose duty involves supporting and developing CI.

Rituals

Repetition provided by ritual communicative practices allows for stability and security within the community, a reinforcing of established professional identity and shared sense of meaning.

Translating

A central work task of CI professionals involves translating new and complex computational methods and tools to new users.

Collaborating

Because reliance on grant funding and the interdisciplinary nature of big data-related problems, CI professionals often collaborate on projects.

Sharing Spaces

Although CI involves digital technologies, physical spaces provide camaraderie and personal support for CI professionals.

Interpreting Guidance

The CI community must always interpret and enact guidance from funding agencies and/or the universities where CI-related centers are often housed.

Justifying

Because CI represents an expensive and large-scale commitment, CI professionals must always justify why the commitment is worth the effort.

Riots

Riot communicative practices are disruptive and noteworthy instances of communication that push the community to adapt.

Contradicting Rituals

CI professionals must negotiate conflicting priorities and behaviors caused by contradicting ritual practices.

Competing

CI professionals compete for limited resources and funding, thus must adapt to remain cutting edge.

Evangelizing

To further grow the innovation, CI professionals evangelize new users and workers—both getting the word out about CI and incorporating people into the community.

Questioning

Points of failure within the community or responses to criticisms can lead to CI professionals questioning their behavior and identity and adapting to respond.

Listening

CI professionals listen to different stakeholders, such as users, internal members, and funding agencies, to adapt to changing circumstances.